
Machine Learning in Textual Data of Cardiovascular Disease via Phrase Mining and Network Embedding

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Abstract

The Medline Database comprises a treasure trove of over 2.2 million cardiovascular-related scientific articles, which are largely in unstructured data, making it a formidable challenge to identify datasets and to comprehend information. We aim to address this big data challenge by developing novel text-mining and machine-learning techniques to dissect textual data, to identify patterns in datasets, and to reveal mechanistic insights. Textual datasets containing six cardiovascular diseases (CVD) were used as the validating corpus. We applied a combination of novel

phrase-mining algorithms, namely SegPhrase+ and ToPMine, and a newly developed phrased-based networking embedding technique, Large-scale Information Network Embedding (LINE) to create the Context-aware Semantic Online Analytical Processing (CaseOLAP) workflow. Our text-mining approach is the first study using CaseOLAP on textual data of cardiovascular health and disease, and highlights cardiovascular protein-disease relationships. We believe this approach affords promising biomedical and clinical applications including pattern discovery in accumulated patient information from electronic health records.

1 Introduction & Background

Over the past decades, mounting information on cardiovascular disease (CVD) from natural language in text and social media has been accumulating online. For instance, the Medline Database comprises over 2.2 million cardiovascular related scientific and clinical articles, and it is estimated that there is a new publication available online every 3 minutes [1]. Unfortunately, these massive textual data are often unstructured and even unreliable. Furthermore, unstructured mounting biomedical data from omics studies, electronic health records, clinical trials, and medical diagnostic images are interconnected and provide many new challenges to design biomedical studies and facilitate precision medicine [2]. The rapid growth of biomedical textual data is still unmatched by the limited capacity of current free-text analytical tools, and most information is not properly analyzed or utilized and is even neglected [3, 4]. Hence, we aim to address these big data science challenges by developing novel text-mining and machine learning technologies to dissect textual data in CVD, identify patterns in datasets, and to recognize new mechanistic insights. Our study demonstrates the feasibility of applying phrase-mining and network embedding on textual data in CVD, as well as identifying novel classifications and trends to facilitate predictive analytics. Accordingly, the main aims of our study are: i) to conduct natural language processing and statistical pattern learning on published natural textual databases in 6 main groups of CVD, ii) to explore the application of phrase-mining and network embedding on textual CVD data, extract relevant information and identify novel patterns or classifications, and iii) to facilitate predictive analytics, gain novel mechanistic disease insights, and facilitate clinical decision-making.

2 Methods & Workflow

To recognize patterns and extract information from 6 CVD datasets, we applied a combination of novel cutting-edge phrase-mining algorithms, namely SegPhrase+ and ToPMine [5, 6], and a newly developed phrased-based networking embedding technique Large-scale Information Network Embedding (LINE) (Figure 1). These 6 main CVD groups were Cerebrovascular Accidents (CVA), Cardiomyopathies and heart failure (CM), Ischemic Heart Diseases (IHD), Arrhythmias, Valve Disease (VD), and Congenital Heart Disease (CHD). From the main corpus, we screened 551,358 publications (dating from 1995 to 2016) in the Medline Database using Pubmed as a search engine. To extract articles we applied MeSH-terms from the National Library of Medicine's controlled vocabulary together with non-MeSH-term synonyms in CVD, in parallel with a list of top-250 proteins¹ that are highly relevant in CVD [7]. Within each CVD group, each protein was scored and ranked using Context-aware Semantic Online Analytical Processing (CaseOLAP). CaseOLAP aims to use a set of top-k phrases to summarize the subset of documents associated with a specific concept, which is distinguishable associated sibling concepts. This functionality helps users to quickly understand the semantics of any structured subset of the text collection without having to read a large amount of text, thus improving the capability to navigate and analyze textual data. In our application, CaseOLAP enables us to find top-k representative proteins for each CVD group, where the top-k proteins for one group are distinctive from those in other groups. Accordingly, CaseOLAP proposes three criteria for ranking representative phrases in a subset of documents: i) integrity (e.g., a good phrase often provides an integral semantic unit), ii) popularity (i.e., popular in the current document subset), and iii) distinctiveness (i.e., being able to distinguish the current document subset from others). Integrity is directly derived from the corpus-wise SegPhrase computation. Popularity indicates how significant the presence of a phrase has in the target document subset, which relies on the statistics from documents only within the subset D_c . Rare phrases in a subset should be ranked

¹<https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.4055886.v1>

Figure 1: Workflow of a newly developed Context-aware Semantic Online Analytical Processing (CaseOLAP) to score cardiovascular proteins over vast amounts of textual data. We applied a combination of novel phrase-mining algorithms, namely SegPhrase+ & ToPMine [5, 6], and a newly developed phrase-based networking embedding technique Large-scale Information Network Embedding (LINE). These 6 main CVD groups were Cerebrovascular Accidents (CVA), Cardiomyopathies and heart failure (CM), Ischemic Heart Diseases (IHD), Arrhythmias (AR), Valve Dysfunction (VD), and Congenital Heart Disease (CHD). We screened and evaluated 551,358 publications (dating from 1995 to 2016) in the Medline Database using Pubmed as a search engine. To extract articles and distinguish hidden patterns, we applied MeSH-terms with non-MeSH-term synonyms in CVD. Each protein was scored using Context-aware Semantic Online Analytical Processing (CaseOLAP) and ranked within each CVD group. The final ranked score for each protein was calculated by integrity (meaningfulness and high-quality phrase), popularity (total count in the extracted articles of the CVD) and distinctiveness (count in the extracted articles of a CVD as compared to the 5 other CVDs).

low, while the increase of phrase frequency should have a diminishing return. Distinctiveness is context-sensitive and is subtle to define since it relies on both the documents in the target document subset and those in the contrastive document set. Moreover, using the whole collection as contrastive document set is not sufficient. A more accurate distinctiveness measure requires an appropriate choice of a contrastive document set. For example, to compute the distinctiveness for CVA, sibling document subsets from the five other CVD groups must be considered, as opposed to using the set of all available medical documents. If the set of all medical documents were used, a phrase common in general CVD would be considered distinctive for CVA. The overall ranking score of phrase p in document subset c , $r(p, c)$, is defined as geometric mean of the three abovementioned criteria.

3 Results

IHD led the publication counts (179,727) followed by CVA (160,941 counts) suggesting that these are the two most investigated CVDs. Subsequently, the total publication counts were followed by Arrhythmias (83,912 counts), CHD (55,513 counts), VD (45,575 counts), and CM (25,690 counts). In the next analysis (Figure 2), we displayed the calculated protein scores (according to CaseOLAP) for all 250 proteins relevant to CVD in a heatmap over the 6 main groups of CVD. Interestingly, we identified several protein clusters with a high calculated score that was unique within a specific CVD group indicating that these proteins are more relevant in a certain CVD. Other protein clusters showed a relatively low score unique within a certain CVD group. Moreover, IHD and CVA appeared to be clustered diseases, as well as VD and CHD. We further analyzed the top 5 protein scores within each CVD group. Top-ranked molecules according to their calculated scores in IHD were: cholesteryl ester transfer protein (4.606), apolipoprotein A-I (3.994) and adiponectin (3.652), indicating a strong relevance of lipid metabolism as well as neutrophil granulocytes in

Figure 2: Heatmap of 250 Proteins with their CaseOLAP Scores over Vast Amounts of Cardiovascular Disease Textual Data. The calculated protein scores according to CaseOLAP were depicted in a heat map over the 6 main groups of CVD. We identified several protein clusters with a high calculated score that were unique within a specific CVD group indicating that these proteins are more relevant in certain CVD as compared to others. Conversely, other protein clusters showed a relatively low score unique within a certain CVD group. Moreover, IHD and CVA appeared to be clustered diseases, as well as VD and CHD which is in line with their total number of publication counts. A list of the 250 proteins relevant to CVD together with their protein identification number (Uniprot) can be found at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.4055886.v1> [7]

inflammation. In CVA, α -galactosidase scored (5.911), brain-derived neurotrophic factor (5.597), tissue-type plasminogen (4.948), apolipoprotein E (3.690), and methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (2.715) suggesting that glycoproteins and lipids are highly relevant in CVAs. Interestingly, top protein scores within CM were led by inflammatory molecules, -interferon (3.341), tumor necrosis factor (TNF, 2.550) and interleukin-4 (2.814), interleukin-17a (2.733) and the contractile protein titin (2.353). The majority of the top 5 proteins in Arrhythmias were ion channel components such as ryanodine receptor 2 (3.358), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily H member (2.738) and gap junction alpha-1 protein (1.873). Platelet activating enzyme platelet-activating acetylhydrolase (1.740) and methionine synthase had the highest score (3.799). The top 5 proteins and their calculated scores in VD were mineralocorticoid receptor (3.277), elastin (2.383), tropomyosin alpha-1 chain (2.333), myosin-binding protein c cardiac type (1.702) and platelet-activating factor acetylhydrolase (1.611). Lastly, the top 5 proteins with the highest calculated scores in CHD were fibrillin-1 (4.925), plakophilin-2 (3.215), tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type 11 (2.671), arachidonate 5-Lipoxygenase-activating protein (2.040) and catechol O-methyltransferase (1.789). In the next step of our analysis we selected the top 25 proteins with the highest calculated scores in CM and created a heat map to analyze their relevance over the other CVDs (Figure 3). The top 25 proteins in CM appear to have a similar score pattern in both IHD and CVA with the majority of overlapping proteins revealing an inflammatory function. Accordingly, CVA and IHD were clustered diseases, while valve diseases, congenital heart disease and arrhythmias appear to share little overlap to the 25 top molecules in CM. Furthermore, contractile proteins such as titin have a high relevance in CM as well as VD but not in the other CVDs. As expected, troponin-I had a very high score in IHD as this is a popular biomarker in IHD. Platelet-activating factor acetyl hydrolase which catabolizes platelet activating factor appeared to be relevant in all 6 CVD groups. Interestingly, amyloid beta A4 protein, a biomarker in Alzheimer disease, appeared to be significant in all six CVD groups.

4 Summary

We have demonstrated that a combination of phrase-mining algorithms and a large-scale network embedding technique is effective to annotate vast volumes of CVD textual data for statistical pattern

Figure 3: Heatmap of the Top 25 Protein CaseOLAP Scores in Cardiomyopathy and Heart Failure over the 5 other Main Groups of CVD. The top 25 proteins in CM appear to have a similar score pattern in both IHD and CVA with the majority of proteins overlapping both heart diseases revealing an inflammatory function. CVA and IHD were clustered diseases, while valve Diseases, congenital heart disease and arrhythmias appear to share little overlap to the 25 top molecules in CM. Furthermore, contractile proteins such as titin have a high relevance in CM as well as VD but not in the other CVDs. Troponin-I had a very high score in IHD as this is a popular biomarker in acute coronary syndromes and myocardial infarctions while this had little relevance in CVA. Interestingly, amyloid beta A4 protein, an established protein in Alzheimer disease, appears to be consistent over all six CVD groups. This implicates that Alzheimer proteins may also have biomedical and clinical implication in CVDs.

discovery and information extraction. This machine-learning and text-mining approach was able to screen over half a million published manuscripts within one month, which would have taken 20 years of intense and continuous labor for an individual. Furthermore, this text-mining approach is the first study using CaseOLAP on textual data of cardiovascular health and disease and highlights cardiovascular protein-disease relationships. Accordingly, we gained novel insights into the relationships of 250 proteins and 6 major CVDs. We believe that this text-mining approach has many more promising biomedical and clinical applications including pattern discovery in accumulated patient information from Clinical Case Reports, Human Cohort Studies, Clinical Trials and Electronic Health Records.

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